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ON COMPOSITE HOMOGENIZATION THEORY

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SUMMARY: This paper discusses the composite homogenization theory, which is the foundation for the design and analysis of composites as a structural material. The focus of discussion is placed on the key assumptions made in developing a homogenization method, vis-a-vis their physical implication and modeling consequence; in particular, it is required that the homogenization method provides a two-way passage between the microlevel and macrolevel modeling analyses. Illustrative examples are presented along with numerical results, using unidirectional fiber-reinforced composite systems of known properties.

KEYWORDS: Statistical Homogeneity; Critical-Volume-Element (CVE); Fiber Packing; Material Symmetry; Representative Volume Element (RVE); Effective Composite Property; Bounds; Collapsed Bounds; Rigorous Solutions; Micro/Macro; Two-Way Passage.

INTRODUCTION

It occurs in engineering that any material selected for use in engineering systems should be suitably characterized for purpose of design and analysis. The essence of characterization is two-folds: to extract from the material the pertinent properties in order to predict forward the system (global) response; and to analyze in reverse the material (local) response based on the system response. It is thus necessary to secure a two-way passage between the local and global responses. Ideally, the characterization should be conducted based on the true microstructure of the material, along with a rational analysis methodology. But in many materials, the microstructure is complex; and it is often idealized and/or simplified, just to render practical solutions. It is in this context that an improper characterization can lead to inadequate or even paradoxical results.

For a class of unidirectional (UD) composites, the microstructure at the composite's sub-surface level may include matrix, fiber, coating/interphase, fiber-matrix disbonds, matrix-microvoids, etc. To describe such a microstructure geometrically and materially is difficult if not impractical. Thus, in practice, the microstructure is either idealized or simplified; so a rational analysis methodology can be developed for the conduct of characterization. In this connection, the theory of homogenization has been employed as the fundamental basis for composite characterization. Briefly, the theory attempts to replace the composite which is with an endowed microstructure by an equivalent or abstractive material which is voided of a microstructure. This is often achieved by a sequence of assumptions made in describing the microstructure and in developing the analysis methodology.

The theory has been applied extensively to composites of all kinds; and it is often done without critically examining the limitations and/or consequences of the assumptions made in the characterization process.

The purpose of this paper is to discuss some of the prevailing composite homogenization methodologies; focus is placed on the implications/consequences of the key assumptions made therein. To be definite but without loss of generality, discussions will be confined to UD composites only; numerical results for illustration purpose are computed using known composite systems.

KEY ASSUMPTIONS IN HOMOGENIZATION

Statistical Homogeneity.

Most early works on characterization of UD composites assume statistical homogeneity at the macroscale; see Hill [1], Hashin and Rosen [2] and Christensen and Lo [3]. This assumption leads to a fiber-volume content V_f which exists uniformly in the homogenized composite; extension of this assumption then asserts that other effective properties, much like V_f , also exist uniformly in the homogenized composite.

Existence of a uniform V_f is obviously conditional to the composite microstructure. To explain, examine Fig.1a; it is shown here the magnified cross-section of a UD graphite-epoxy composite; over this cross-section, the average V_f is 0.71. But, at the magnified scale, the fibers are clearly not uniformly distributed; and the local value of V_f varies with the size and location of the volume-element over which V_f is computed. Fig.1b shows the dependence of V_f on the volume-element size; it is seen that V_f scatters greatly when the volume-element is small; the scatter is less and less as the volume-element becomes larger; V_f does converge to 0.71 when the volume-element equals at least 36 fiber cross-sections, or a volume containing 25 or more (36×0.71) fibers.

Thus, V_f is constant at the macroscale only over a sufficiently large volume; the minimum volume over which V_f approaches this constant is termed here the critical volume-element (CVE). Clearly, the significance of the CVE is far reaching; it will be further discussed later.

At this point, it is noted that some UD composites are purposely made with a controlled microstructure; then the variability in the fiber distribution can be minimized or removed. But, in practice, fabrication can still introduce a degree of variability. For instance, Fig.2a shows the cross-section of a boron/epoxy composite where the fiber packing is intended to be a square array; but variability in the fiber distribution still exists. In fact, the average V_f over the cross-section shown is 0.56, while the CVE size is 23 fiber cross-sections, or a volume containing 13 fibers; see Fig.2b.

Material Symmetry.

Another assumption pertains to material symmetry at the macroscale. For UD composites, symmetry is inferred from fiber packing and/or other features at this scale. If only fiber packing is considered and the fiber-matrix bonding is perfect, three symmetry levels are usually assumed: for fiber packing with a rectangular array, orthotropy is assumed; for a square array, it reduces to square symmetry; and for random fiber packing, transversely isotropy is assumed.

It is noted that the assumed symmetry for the latter is only an average property over a sufficiently large volume-element, similar to the CVE required for the material homogeneity assumption.

But in practice, random fiber packing is often simplified. Hashin, et. al. [2], for example, treated random fiber packing as an assemblage of concentric-cylinders; the hexagonal array has also been proposed to mimic random fiber packing. The reason for fiber packing simplification may be two-folds: the first is to be able to identify a suitable representative volume-element (RVE) which is much smaller than the CVE and yet preserves the assumed constant V_f and material symmetry; the second is to minimize the difficulty associated with analyzing anything more complex.

REPRESENTATIVE-VOLUME-ELEMENTS (RVE)

Within the confines of the statistical homogeneity and material symmetry assumptions, a properly selected RVE plays a dominant role in the composite homogenization process. Here, two general classes of RVE models are discussed, along with their implications in the homogenization process.

Single-Fiber Models.

Most early works use 2-phase single-fiber models. For instance, the concentric-cylinder model used by Hashin and Rosen [2] is consisted of a single fiber surrounded by a matrix ring, see Fig.3a. The model is intended for random or hexagonal fiber packing; but it neglects interactions with its surrounding fibers, a major undesirable short-coming.

A modification of the concentric-cylinder model is the 3-phase self-consistent model, such as used by Christensen and Lo [3]. This model contains a single fiber, a matrix ring and another outside ring with infinite expanse; the material in the outside ring is none other than the homogenized composite itself, see Fig.3b. Introduction of the outer composite ring thus provides an approximate effect of fiber interaction.

Multiple-Fiber Models.

With increased computation power, multiple-fiber models are used in recent years. In general, multiple-fiber models alleviate the short-comings inherent in the single-fiber models. Here, two such models are discussed: the periodic array model and the random array model.

The periodic array model is intended for regular fiber packing, such as rectangular/square array. In essence, the RVE is infinite in expanse; it is composed contiguously of just one kind of repeating unit-cells; when under load, each and every unit-cell in the RVE must be deformed in the same way. Under such conditions, only one in-situ unit-cell needs to be isolated (see Fig.3c) and analyzed under periodic boundary conditions (see Yuan and Pagano [4]). This model assures rigorous inclusion of the fiber interaction effect.

The random array model may contain any number of fibers, so long as it can adequately represent the fiber packing, be it regularly packed or randomly packed. As examples, Fig.3d shows a 9-fiber RVE for the square array and Fig.3e, a 8-fiber RVE for the hexagonal array. In both cases,

periodicity is not invoked but both contain a center-element as shown. This single-fiber center-element can be taken as an insitu RVE; and it functions similarly as the single-fiber unit-cell in the periodic array model. Since the random array RVE does not require regularity or periodicity in the fiber packing, it can be as large as the CVE if random fiber packing is considered. In that case, the center-element may contain more than a single fiber. This last point will be further discussed along with numerical results later in this paper.

RVE ANALYSIS APPROACHES

The premise for finding the effective properties of the homogenization composite is through the averaging procedure. For instance, to obtain the effective elastic stiffness \mathbf{C} , one first solves the boundary-value (B-V) problem associated with the chosen RVE; solutions for the stress \mathbf{s} and strain \mathbf{e} are then averaged over the RVE to yield \mathbf{s}_0 and \mathbf{e}_0 ; and these are then considered the effective stress/strain of the homogenized composite at the macroscale. The stiffness \mathbf{C} is determined through the generalized Hooke's law $\mathbf{s}_0 = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{e}_0$ (see [2]). Clearly, the accuracy of the stiffness \mathbf{C} depends on how realistically the RVE is chosen and how rigorously the B-V problem is solved.

The inherent difficulty in the B-V problem is that the RVE is isolated from the composite in bulk, and there are mixed stresses and strains (or displacement) distributed on its boundary; these boundary agencies are the solutions rather than the prescribed boundary conditions of the B-V problem. Hence, in practice, many approximate methods are used to estimate the constants in \mathbf{C} , such as the rule-of-mixture, the iso-strain, iso-stress models, etc. In the following, two relatively rigorous solution methods are discussed.

Bounding and Collapsed Bounds.

The bounding method was developed by Hashin and Rosen [2] for determining the elastic constants in the stiffness \mathbf{C} for UD composites. Briefly, if uniform strain \mathbf{e}_0 is prescribed on the boundary of the RVE, it implies that the material surrounding the RVE is made more stiff than it actually is; thus the resulting solution for \mathbf{C} represents an upper-bound estimate; on the other hand, if a uniform stress \mathbf{s}_0 is prescribed, the material surrounding the RVE is made softer than it actually is; so the resulting \mathbf{C} is a lower-bound estimate.

The method can be applied to both single-fiber models and multi-fiber models. In general, the bounds for \mathbf{C} obtained using a single-fiber model is wider than that obtained using a multi-fiber model. In particular, by bounding the multi-fiber model (such as shown in Fig.3d and 3e) one can consider the insitu center-element alone and perform the averaging procedure over just this element for the bounds of \mathbf{C} . Often than not, the upper and lower bounds would collapse into one.

Bounds-collapsing signifies that a near-rigorous solution is found for the center-element; it also means that the micro stress/strain fields in and near the center-element is insensitive to the boundary conditions prescribed in solving the parent (multi-fiber) RVE problem, be it the constant strain \mathbf{e}_0 or the constant stress \mathbf{s}_0 , as long as they are effectively equivalent.

This last point is an assurance that the micro stress/strain fields in and near the center element in the multi-fiber RVE can be recovered near-rigorously once the effective \mathbf{e}_0 and \mathbf{s}_0 fields are obtained from the global analysis.

Rigorous Solutions.

The B-V problem associated with the 3-phase single-fiber self-consistent RVE model such as shown in Fig.3b can be solved rigorously without having to resort to bounding or other compromised solution techniques, see [3].

Similarly, the B-V problem associated with the periodic element model, Fig.3c, can also be solved rigorously, although it often requires a numerical routine such as the finite element method, see [4].

It is noted, however, that solution to the former entails a certain degree of approximation due to the simplified RVE representation; the latter is rigorous only within the confine of the periodic assumption imposed on the RVE which is infinite in expanse.

Numerical Illustrations.

The various points discussed above can be illustrated more vividly using numerical results. The specific composite considered here is typical of a glass/epoxy UD composite, with the fiber and matrix assumed linearly elastic and isotropic; fiber and matrix are assumed perfectly bonded. The elastic constants of the fiber and matrix are: $E_f=73$ GPa; $\nu_f=0.22$; $E_m=3.45$ GPa; $\nu_m=0.35$.

For conciseness, only the effective shear modulus G_{23} or G_{yz} will be displayed as a function of V_f , where the axis-1 or x is in the fiber direction and the 23- or yz-plane is transverse to the fiber. Clearly, for composites such as considered here the elastic properties in the transverse plane are more sensitive to fiber packing details.

Fig.4a displays 3 sets of G_{23} results for RVEs based on simplified fiber packing for random array: that of the 2-phase single-fiber RVE used by Hashin and Rosen [2] to establish the upper and lower bounds; that of the 3-phase single-fiber self-consistent RVE used by Christensen and Lo [3] to obtain the rigorous solution; and that of the 8-fiber RVE for hexagonal array (Fig.3e), wherein the insitu center-element is used to obtain the collapsed bounds. It is seen that the bounds from solving the single-fiber model is rather wide; but the bounds obtained from the center-element of the 8-fiber model collapse essentially into one. The self-consistent model appears to be fairly close to the collapsed bounds, but not the same; the slight difference is obviously due to the approximate nature of the self-consistent RVE representation. Note that G_{23} is only one of 5 independent elastic constants in the stiffness \mathbf{C} .

Fig.4b also displays 3 sets of G_{yz} for the square array; here y-z are axes of the square symmetry and G_{yz} is one of 6 independent constants \mathbf{C} . In this figure, the pair of wide bounds is obtained by bounding the 9-fiber RVE shown in Fig.3d; the pair of collapsed bounds is obtained by using only the center-element in the 9-fiber parent RVE. The darkened dots which fall on the collapsed bounds are rigorous solutions from solving the periodic-element model shown in Fig.3c. Thus, the collapsed-bounds can be considered as near-rigorous solutions.

The last point can be further illustrated by examining Fig.5a and 5b. Fig.5a shows the exaggerated deformed configuration of the insitu unit-cell or center-element; Fig.5b is the periodic component of the deformed configuration (see [4] or [5]); both are results obtained by solving the periodic-element model and by bounding the center-element of the 9-fiber model as explained above. No difference could be discerned in these results.

THE MICRO/MACRO TWO-WAY PASSAGE

From defining RVE to determining the effective properties of the UD composite constitutes the forward passage that enables analysis methods to be developed for structures made of the composite. Upon the analysis of the structure under load, the effective stress/strain fields in the composite are obtained. At that point, the analyst has two options: one is to use the computed effective stress/strain fields directly to predict the microlevel responses in the composite, such as failure initiation and failure mechanisms; the other is to use the same effective stress/strain fields as boundary conditions to be imposed on the RVE and solve the B-V problem in order to recover the true microlevel responses.

The former option is often taken in practice, despite of warnings of possible breakdown (see Hart-smith [6]), especially when the effective fields contain singularity or highly localized stress/strain gradients (see Pagano and Yuan [7]). With the backward passage, the key question is whether the RVE used in the backward passage can recover the responses uniquely.

This question can now be answered with reasonable assurance. In the previous discussion of the multi-fiber RVE with a center-element, it was shown that the micro stress/strain fields in and near the element remain virtually unchanged regardless whether a stress or a strain condition is applied on the boundary of the RVE. Thus, in the backward passage, a proper multi-fiber RVE should be used and the center-element should be situated in the localized, high-gradient effective stress zone; furthermore, the RVE should be large enough so that on its boundary the effective stress/strain should contain no or very low gradient. In fact, in view of the statistical homogeneity and material symmetry assumptions for random fiber packing, one should consider the CVE instead of a smaller RVE; the center-element may then contain several fibers and the boundary of the CVE is further away from the high gradient zone.

The above observation has been confirmed by several detailed example problems, worked out by the present authors and independently by others [8]; owing to the length limit of this paper, however, that part of the results will be presented elsewhere.

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Fig. 1. (a) Cross-section of a graphite/epoxy UD system; (b) Dependence of V_f on area-element over which V_f is computed.

Fig. 2. (a) Cross-section of a boron/epoxy UD system; (b) Dependence of V_f on area-element over which V_f is computed.

Fig. 3. (a) 2-phase single-fiber RVE; (b) 3-phase single-fiber RVE; (c) Unit-cell in periodic array; (d) 9-fiber RVE in square array; (e) 8-fiber RVE in hexagonal array.

Fig. 4. (a) Computed G_{23} as a function of V_f for random/hexagonal array; (b) Computed G_{xy} as a function of V_f for square array.

Fig. 5 (a) The deformed unit-cell/center-element under effective pure shear; (b) the periodic component of the deformation in (a).